

Applicability of Linear Free Energy Relationships. Oxidation of Amines by Cerium(IV) in Presence and Absence of Silver(I)[†]

M ANAND RAO

Department of Chemistry, College of Technology, Osmania University, Hyderabad-500 007

Manuscript received 10 March 1986, revised 8 December 1986, accepted 17 February 1987

The effect of structure on the rates of oxidation of aliphatic amines by Ce^{4+} in nitric acid medium under uncatalysed conditions and in the presence of Ag^+ has been studied. Taft's plot was linear with a slope (ρ^*) of -5.30 for uncatalysed reactions. In case of Ag^+ catalysed reaction, the preequilibrium step, viz. formation of an adduct between Ag^+ and amine was influenced by both polar and steric effects as seen from the ρ^* and δ values ($\rho^* = -3.13 \pm 0.04$ and $\delta = -0.246 \pm 0.02$). However, the rates of oxidation of these adducts in the slow step were influenced by only polar effect ($\rho^* = -2.90$)

IN the oxidation of amines by various oxidants¹⁻⁴, two distinct mechanisms, one involving dehydrogenation and the other an attack at the lone-pair electrons of nitrogen have been suggested. In the present study, the possibility of attack of the oxidant at N—H bond of the amine is ruled out on the basis of the observed rate of oxidation of trimethylamine by Ce^{IV} ⁵. But, the product analysis did not help to understand the above two possibilities, because from both routes the same type of products can be obtained. In order to find out which one of the above routes is operative, the rate data (obtained for the oxidation of amines by Ce^{4+} under uncatalysed and Ag^+ catalysed conditions) were analysed by applying the Taft's linear free energy relationships.

Results and Discussion

Uncatalysed reaction⁵: In the uncatalysed oxidation, the attack of the oxidant on amine might be expected to take place in two ways, (i) attack on α -C—H of amine and (ii) direct attack on lone-pair of electrons on nitrogen of the amine. In the former case, isopropylamine would have to be taken as the standard compound of the series (for which Taft's σ^* and E_s values are zero) as it contains two methyl groups on the α -carbon atom. In such a case, some of the σ^* and E_s values for the substituents attached to α -carbon should be taken for correlating the rate data. The computed $\Sigma\sigma^*$ and ΣE_s values are given in Table 1. Using these values Taft's equations were applied to rate data and was found that none of them applicable. This rules out the possibility of the attack of oxidant on α -C—H bond. For the other possibility, viz. direct attack on lone-pair of electrons on nitrogen of amine, methylamine has to be taken as a standard

one of the series. The rate data for various substituents along with their σ^* and E_s values are given in Table 1. The plot of $\log k'$ against σ^* gave a

TABLE 1—RATE DATA IN UNCATALYSED OXIDATION OF AMINES BY Ce^{IV}

$[Ce^{IV}] = 0.005 M$, $[HNO_3] = 0.500 M$, $[Amine] = 0.400 M$
Temp = 328 K

Amine radical	$k' \times 10^4$ $dm^3 mol^{-1} s^{-1}$	σ^*	E_s	$\Sigma\sigma^*$	ΣE_s
Hydrogen	—	+0.490	+1.24	—	—
Methyl	1.40	0.000	0.000	0.980	2.48
Ethyl	4.60	-0.100	-0.070	0.490	1.24
n-Propyl	4.67	-0.115	-0.360	0.390	1.17
n-Butyl	7.48	-0.130	-0.390	0.375	0.880
Isopropyl	13.9	-0.190	-0.470	0.000	0.000
Isobutyl	6.63	-0.245	-0.930	0.300	0.770

straight line ($\gamma=0.987$) with a slope (ρ^*) -5.30 , supporting the fact that there is a direct attack of the oxidant at lone pair of electrons on nitrogen. The polar effects on the rates of oxidation of amines receive further support from the correlation of $\Delta\Delta G^\ddagger$ values. The difference in values of $\Delta G^\ddagger$ of any amine to that of methylamine) with the polar interaction energies (P) calculated from the equation⁶, $P = -2.303 RT \rho^* \sigma^*$ (Table 2).

Ag^+ -catalysed reaction⁴: If the formation of adduct between Ag^+ and amine is taken as first step, and attack of the oxidant on this adduct as the next slow step, the formation constants (K) and the second order rate constant (k'') for the slow step can be calculated⁷ (Table 3) from the slope and intercept values of the linear plots of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[amine]$. Further, the plots of neither $\log K$ vs

[†]Presented at the National Seminar on Linear Free Energy Relationships (Correlation Analysis), Madras, 1985.

TABLE 2— $\Delta\Delta G^\ddagger$ VALUES IN Ag^+ -CATALYSED AND -UNCATALYSED REACTIONS

Amine	Catalysed		Uncatalysed	
	$\Delta\Delta G^\ddagger$ $\text{J K}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$	P	$\Delta\Delta G^\ddagger$ $\text{J K}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$	P
Methyl	0	0	0	0
Ethyl	1 600	1 818	3 000	3 362
n-Propyl	2 000	2 091	4 000	3 867
n-Butyl	2 900	2 363	5 000	4 871
Isopropyl	3 200	3 454	5 400	5 120
Isobutyl	2 300	2 272	4 000	4 203

TABLE 3—FORMATION CONSTANTS (K) AND RATE CONSTANTS (k'') IN Ag^+ -CATALYSED OXIDATION OF AMINES AT 323 K

Amine	k''	K
	$\times 10^2 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$	$\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
Methyl	1.78	1.40
Ethyl	3.27	3.12
n-Propyl	3.79	4.33
n-Butyl	5.25	4.98
Isopropyl	5.95	6.93
Isobutyl	4.17	6.15

σ^* nor $\log K$ vs E_s are linear (Fig. 1A) indicating that formation constants are not alone the function of either polar or steric effects. Assuming the contribution due to both the effects in the formation of adduct (K), Taft's four parameter equation⁶ ($\log K = \rho^* \sigma^* + \delta E_s + \log K_0$) was applied to the formation constants. Using the method of solving simultaneous equations⁶, it was found that the formation constants could be fitted well into the

Fig. 1. (A) Plot of $\log K$ vs σ^* , (B) plot of $(\log K - \delta E_s)$ vs σ^* , and (C) Plot of $(2 + \log k'')$ vs σ^* .

equation with $\rho^* = -3.13 \pm 0.04$, $\delta = -0.246 \pm 0.02$ and the correlation coefficient was 0.992 (Fig. 1B). However, plot of $\log k''$ vs σ^* was linear ($r = 0.985$) with a slope, $\rho^* = -2.90$ (Fig 1C), suggesting that the oxidation of Ag^+ -amine adduct is governed mainly by polar effects. Further, the trends in $\Delta\Delta G^\ddagger$ values are also in line with the values of polar interaction energies (P) (Table 3) indicating that only polar effects are operative during the oxidation of Ag^+ -amine adducts by Ce^{IV} .

Thus the structure-reactivity correlation on Ag^+ -catalysed oxidation of amines by Ce^{IV} indicates that while the formation constants (K) are affected by polar as well as steric effects, the rates of oxidation of adducts by Ce^{4+} are affected only by polar effects as in the case of uncatalysed⁵ oxidation of amines by Ce^{4+} . From the above discussion it is clear that in case of uncatalysed reaction, the orientation effects play an insignificant role, while in the Ag^+ -catalysed reactions, proper orientation between Ag^+ and amine is required to form an adduct which later reacts with Ce^{4+} to give the products. Rate of uncatalysed Ce^{4+} -amine reaction is more sensitive to substituent effects ($\rho^* = -5.30$) than Ce^{4+} -adduct reaction ($\rho_{\text{adduct}}^* = -2.90$). In the catalysed reactions, substituents affect both the formation of the adducts ($\rho_K^* = -3.13$) as well as the rate of oxidation of these adducts by Ce^{4+} .

Acknowledgement

The author is grateful to Prof. T. Navaneeth Rao, Vice-Chancellor, Osmania University and Prof. B. Sethuram, Head, Department of Chemistry, Osmania University, Hyderabad, for helpful discussions and encouragement.

References

- S. S. RAWALAY and H. SHECHTER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1967, 32, 3129.
- M. LIMIHAILOVIC, A. STOJILJKOVIC and ANDREJEVIC, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1965, 461.
- D. H. ROSENBLATT, A. J. HAYES, JR., B. L. HOROSON, R. A. STRENTLY and K. A. MOORE, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1963, 28, 2790.
- R. A. SHEIK and W. A. WATERS, *J. Chem Soc. (B)*, 1970, 988.
- M. A. RAO, B. SETHURAM and T. N. RAO, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, 19, 747.
- W. A. PAVELICH and R. W. TAFT, JR., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 79, 4935.
- M. A. RAO, B. SETHURAM and T. N. RAO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982 59, 1040.
- R. L. ANDERSON and T. A. BANCROFT, "Statistical Theory in Research", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1952, Chap. 14.